

Challenges faced by students in online English courses during the COVID-19 pandemic

Ketut Susiani¹, Nyoman Dantes², Ida Bagus Putu Arnyana³, Ni Ketut Suarni², Kadek Suranata²,
I Kadek Suartama⁴, Alexander Hamonangan Simamora⁴

¹Department Basic of Education, Faculty of Science Education, Universitas Pendidikan Ganesha, Singaraja, Indonesia

²Department Guidance and Counseling, Faculty of Science Education, Universitas Pendidikan Ganesha, Singaraja, Indonesia

³Department of Natural Sciences, Faculty of Mathematics and Natural Sciences, Universitas Pendidikan Ganesha, Singaraja, Indonesia

⁴Department Technology of Education, Faculty of Science Education, Universitas Pendidikan Ganesha, Singaraja, Indonesia

Article Info

Article history:

Received Sep 13, 2023

Revised Oct 28, 2023

Accepted Dec 22, 2023

Keywords:

COVID-19

English

Non english

Online learning

Student challenges

ABSTRACT

Online learning is a growing trend in education during the corona virus disease (COVID-19) pandemic. The purpose of this study is to ascertain the difficulties that online majors in non-English languages have when attempting to acquire English. The subject of this study involved using the questionnaire method for as many as 412 students and interviewing 15 students with a total of 17 questions. The results of this study indicate that there are several challenges faced by students during online learning; i) less familiarity with online learning as shown by 31% of students agreeing that online learning is a new learning method, ii) psychologically 30% of students choose strongly agree that they have limited opportunities to interact directly and freely with lecturers as well as with students, iii) limited facilities and infrastructure as much as 28% agree that the budget is limited to get quota or internet credit, and iv) limited internet access as many as 35% of students do not have good internet coverage to take online lectures. The findings of this study should be a reference for English lecturers to continue learning to innovate in providing online English learning by considering the existing challenges.

This is an open access article under the [CC BY-SA](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/) license.

Corresponding Author:

Ketut Susiani

Departement Basic of Education, Faculty of Science Education, Universitas Pendidikan Ganesha

Udayana Street No. 11 Singaraja Bali, Indonesia

Email: ketut.susiani@undiksha.ac.id

1. INTRODUCTION

The COVID-19 pandemic, which emerged in early 2020, has significantly affected various industries, including education [1]. Consequently, significant transformations have occurred within the education system in Indonesia. To mitigate the spread of corona virus disease (COVID-19), all universities and institutions must cease their operations. The Minister of Education and Culture, Nadiem Makarim, has confirmed several policies, which include the elimination of the national examination, modifications to the school examination system, revisions to the regulations for new student admission, and the implementation of online learning as stated in the Circular of the Ministry of Education and Culture Number 4 of 2020 regarding "Implementation of education policies in the emergency period for the spread of COVID-19" [2]–[7].

One of the policies that have become a popular issue and affects education in Indonesia is the determination to learn from home (online learning). Online learning is said to be a popular issue because it has a major impact on all levels of education from elementary to tertiary levels. Moreover, circular Letter No.

15 of 2020, which addresses guidelines for organizing home-based learning during a COVID-19 emergency, was also released by the Ministry of Education and Culture [8]. These circular states that the goals of implementing learning from home are to protect residents of education units from the negative effects of COVID-19, guarantee students' rights to educational services during the COVID-19 emergency, and stop the spread and transmission of Colorado virus-19 in Indonesia. instruction units and guarantee that teachers, students, and parents receive the necessary psychological support [9].

The decision to study online or from home as a result of the COVID-19 epidemic has given rise to a comprehensive picture of how technology will continue to support education in the future [9] notes that in addition to modifications made to the educational system due to the epidemic, learning is now done via online media and distant learning utilizing computers, laptops, or mobile devices [10]. According to references [11], [12], the COVID-19 epidemic has caused a shift in the educational system from a traditional one to one that uses electronic media and online resources. Therefore, online learning, which was usually a complementary medium in learning in the era before the COVID-19 pandemic, became an alternative that was deemed appropriate for teachers to replace the face-to-face system during this pandemic. This statement is reinforced by the Ministry of Education and Culture [8] that in online or distance learning students can use 23 pages as learning resources.

U.S. Department of Education [13], 2010 Online learning is defined as learning that involves the use of the internet as a whole [12], [14]. On the other hand, online learning is a learning system that does not meet face-to-face but uses a platform that can help the teaching and learning process that is carried out even though it is distanced [15], [16]. In addition to platforms, online learning systems involve the internet network and supporting devices such as smartphones, laptops, or computers [17]–[21]. The online learning system is implemented by all education units and levels of education so that it is considered capable of being a solution to public unrest in carrying out the teaching and learning process in the midst of a pandemic.

Online learning is considered the right solution during a pandemic, but it is unavoidable that there are challenges that come with it. The current pandemic condition forces all elements to be ready to do online learning. Educators, both teachers, and lecturers are required to master teaching using technology and various learning platforms to support it quickly and consistently. Consistent is meant to provide online learning from material presentation, assignment assignments, and learning activities, to the final assessment in one semester. Teachers or lecturers are required to provide learning materials in the form of PPT, PDF, and videos, which must later be uploaded on the learning platform. This is what makes both teachers and lecturers race against time to learn the use of learning platforms or applications that support the continuity of online learning.

Some applications that can help the online teaching and learning process are ZOOM, Schoology, Edmodo, and web blog [18], [19], [22], [23]. This is of course so that the learning objectives can still be achieved as the face-to-face learning system was usually done before the pandemic. One of the state universities in Indonesia that have implemented an online learning system since the even semester of 2020. This online learning requires not only lecturers but also students to equip themselves with all the facilities needed so that teaching and learning activities can run as expected. Lecturers and students are required to facilitate themselves with electronic media to support learning, such as PCs containing learning support applications. Lecturers are also required to master online teaching techniques and students are expected to be able to apply the learning platforms agreed with the lecturers.

The integration of online learning systems is essential for incorporating English into universities' personality development courses. English courses are offered to students who are not part of the English department as a mandatory subject in the basic education department. The courses offered during the early and high semesters prioritize the mastery of English as a crucial skill for all students. These courses aim to serve as a platform for enhancing personal growth and development. The purpose of learning English is to provide students with proficient oral and written English skills, enabling them to effectively acquire specific knowledge and abilities, as well as meet their communication requirements in daily life. The training covers the skills of listening, speaking, reading, and writing.

Regarding the application of online teaching for English in general courses, which is the first time it has been consistently implemented from the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic, there are many things that need to be considered, such as the materials, strategies, and platforms used. The learning process from conventional to online learning of course contains various responses from students, both positive and negative. Moreover, the research focuses on the point of view of non-English majoring students towards online learning of English courses. This study aims to determine the difficulties experienced by students in the Education Department who are not fluent in English when participating in online English classes. So that lecturers in general English subjects can identify things that are a challenge to this online learning system for students.

COVID-19 is a contagious illness caused by a specific strain of coronavirus that was initially identified in Wuhan, China, in December 2019 [20], [21], [23], [24]. The world health organization (WHO)

formally designated the COVID-19 as a pandemic on March 9, 2020. Consequently, the coronavirus has achieved extensive global dissemination. The death toll in cases of COVID-19 has soared across the country. In Indonesia, the death rate for COVID-19 reached 152,745 people as of March 16, 2022 [25].

The epidemic has not only affected the economy and transportation, but also the field of education. To mitigate the transmission of COVID-19, the WHO advises refraining from engaging in activities that could potentially lead to the formation of large gatherings. Hence, the Indonesian government implemented a social distancing strategy, which was subsequently enforced through Circular Letter of the Ministry of Education and Culture, Directorate of Higher Education No. 1 of 2020 [8], aimed at mitigating the transmission of COVID-19 within the education sector. These circular mandates the Ministry of Education and Culture to arrange for remote learning and studying from home (study from home/SFH). This policy came to be recognized as online learning [26].

– English as a foreign language

At the end of the 20th century, English has become a lingua franca, which means that a language is widely used to communicate between people who do not speak the same language [26]–[29]. With this, English has become a world language that provides benefits, namely making it easier for us to interact and communicate with other countries [30]. English as a foreign language (EFL) refers to an approach to learning English for people living in their own country where English is not the dominant or official language [31], [32]. EFL means that English is not used in formal communication and/or communication in daily activities [33]. According to Mauranen [34], English has attained the status of a global language, signifying that numerous countries across the globe see English as their secondary language. In addition, there are several other reasons that support the importance of English, namely [35]:

- a. English opens a window to the world
- b. English provides ample opportunities to study in the best schools or colleges in the world
- c. By mastering English, traveling anywhere in the world will be easy
- d. Provide better job opportunities
- e. Make it easier to make friends
- f. Train the brain.

– Learning in network (online)

Online learning has become the biggest revolution in the world of education. This makes a very big change in the education system and opens up wide opportunities for everyone who wants to learn something [36]. On the other hand [37], [38] states that online learning is a learning activity where the delivery material is delivered via a network. Online learning is conducted through the use of electronic devices, such as tablets, smartphones, laptops, and PCs, which rely on an internet connection for remote access [16], [39].

Online education utilizes internet technology to provide students with instructional content through video tutorials, presentations, and written materials. The primary objective is to provide students with knowledge and facilitate self-paced learning. Similar to every other educational approach, online learning possesses both advantages and difficulties. Gaining insight into the advantages and obstacles of online education will enable institutions to develop more streamlined approaches for disseminating educational resources and guarantee an uninterrupted learning experience for students [40]. The challenges of online learning are; inability to focus on layers, technology problems, feeling isolated, a lack of trained teachers, and too long in front of layers.

Meanwhile, Sunhaji *et al.* [41] postgraduate director of Institut Agama Islam Negeri Purwokerto said the education system, spanning from primary to higher education, today employs technology-driven learning methods. This includes online learning processes, seminars, and lectures that simulate real-world work experiences. The integration of technology in education is a formidable challenge and even a potential menace to institutions that lack familiarity with technological tools. According to Huang [42], there are three primary obstacles in online education. Initially, there is a restricted amount of time available for the preparation and/or modification of offline learning materials to be suitable for online use. Furthermore, the absence or restricted opportunities for direct and unrestricted interaction between teachers and students during online learning leads to the disruption of the learning process. Furthermore, the implementation of a proficient instructional strategy necessitates further exertion in stimulating and engaging students in the context of online education. Online learning can lead to student isolation [43].

2. METHOD

2.1. Research design

The research design encompasses the systematic integration of various study components in a unified and logical manner. This study is a qualitative descriptive investigation. Qualitative descriptive research is a research method that seeks to accurately depict and characterize existing occurrences or events

without altering the variables under investigation. Qualitative descriptive research is commonly known as a naturalistic research method due to its execution in natural situations or settings.

2.2. Participants

This research was conducted at Universitas Pendidikan Ganesha (Undiksha). Involving students majoring in non-English as a sample of 412 students. The students involved were third semester students of the 412 students came from several departments including the Department Basic of Education, Balinese language, and the Civics department.

2.3. Data collection techniques and instruments

The data gathering methods employed in this study involved the use of questionnaires and interviews. The questionnaire to be utilized is an open-ended questionnaire, wherein the researcher has supplied answer options, but the responder is also allowed to offer written responses to further elaborate on their answers. The purpose of interviews, observation and documentation of this research is to obtain data that is as it is without being under certain conditions, the results of which emphasize meaning.

2.4. Data analysis

The data obtained in this study is qualitative in nature, and so, qualitative descriptive analysis is employed for data processing, in line with the research problem. This technique is employed to analyze and make sense of the data description that has been acquired. The data will be transcribed from the questionnaires and interviews. The data collected from the questionnaire responses will be categorized and interpreted to derive conclusions. The data analysis procedure in this study involves the selection, determination, simplification, and descriptive interpretation of the data. Furthermore, data reduction will be implemented to mitigate any potential bias in the research findings.

3. FINDINGS AND ANALYSIS

3.1. Findings

Originating from questionnaire data that has been distributed to respondents, the results obtained will be discussed based on the components of challenges in online learning. This aspect was developed into 17 statement items that were used as a reference in digging up information in the questionnaire instrument which was distributed to students via a link on the google form application. In addition, unstructured interviews were also conducted to obtain more in-depth information on the statement items in the instrument. The questionnaire respondents were 412 students from 18 groups and 15 students were unstructured interview respondents. Data from the questionnaires and unstructured interviews will be discussed based on the dimensions of challenges in learning English online.

3.1.1. Less familiar with online learning

– Learners must adapt to new learning methods

Learning English online is indeed the only way to reduce the spread of COVID-19 in the campus environment. Although online learning at Undiksha has been implemented for a year or 2 semesters before, many students do not feel that online learning, especially in English courses, is a new learning method for them. This can be seen from Figure 1 regarding questionnaire tabulation data about student responses to online learning.

Figure 1. Student responses to online learning

The data presented indicates that a considerable proportion of students, specifically 120 (29%) and 111 (27%), expressed strong disagreement and disagreement respectively, with the notion that studying English online is a novel approach for them. While there are 52 (13%) students answered in doubt, then 65 (16%) students agreed and 64 (15%) the rest stated strongly agree. These data are supported by the interview excerpts as; P6 (question number 6): "...actually, online lectures have been around for a year, but until now, I still feel limited when studying online...". P3: "... from me, actually I don't feel anything about the online learning system because all courses use the online system...".

From the quote, students perceive online learning as a familiar approach considering the learning system from home they have been doing since last year or the previous 2 semesters. So, they are obliged to do online learning and it is an absolute thing to do according to the regulations set by the government. Regarding the statement item in Figure 2 Student feedback on online learning challenges, which states that online learning is a new method, the next statement item is the difficulty of adapting to the online English learning system. In contrast to student responses to the first statement item, the second statement item actually shows that 25 (6%) students answered strongly disagree, 88 (22%) students disagreed, 120 (29%) other students answered undecided, 129 (31%) students agreed, and 50 (12%) others stated strongly agree. The tabulated data from the questionnaire can be observed in Figure 2 titled " Student feedback on online learning challenges".

Figure 2. Student feedback on online learning challenges

The Figure 2 is supported by excerpts from interviews related to online learning constraints during this pandemic. Below is an excerpt from the interview related to the data. P3: ... Continue to adapt to the online learning environment. I don't feel comfortable studying online because sometimes responding to greetings from lecturers can be noisy or time-consuming. It's like saying 'yes' or 'permit to ask', that if everyone asks, the class becomes noisy and not conducive because everyone turns on the speakers. P12: ... What I most often experience is the problem with adapting to the online learning system because I usually study face-to-face but now, I have to use a laptop. I can't focus in front of the laptop for long. The problem is that our schedule for studying one-course session is quite long and not just one course in one day, so because it takes so long in front of the laptop sometimes the focus becomes less.

– Students' attention is easily distracted

The third statement item elucidates the ramifications of online learning itself, in accordance with the second statement item. The third point of the statement is that it is easy for students to be diverted to other sites because they are not familiar with learning English online. The data from the Figure 3 showed that in the third statement item, 37 (9%) students answered strongly disagree, and 168 (41%) students said they did not agree with the statement. While 91 (22%) students expressed doubt, 70 (17%) Out of the students surveyed, a majority responded with agreement, however a smaller percentage, specifically 46 students or 11% of the total, strongly agreed with the statement. The tabulated data from the questionnaire can be observed in Figure 3, along with relevant excerpts from interviews pertaining to the data. P12: ... sometimes when I'm bored waiting for my turn to answer or pause, I open my cellphone every now and then to reply to WA messages or receive calls but not often, because I'm waiting for my turn to answer. However, if the lecturer is explaining the material, I have to focus on listening because it is usually followed by a question-and-answer session. So, if you don't focus, you're afraid of being late and you can't answer when you're appointed. P2: ... if I continue to follow the google meet link because I use a cellphone if I open another site, my cellphone becomes slow and I'm afraid that I will suddenly leave the virtual meeting because I pressed

the wrong button. I've had an experience like that before, that's why I don't dare to open another link if I use my cellphone for virtual meetings.

From the interview data, information was obtained that online learning sometimes feels boring when faced with a too-long exposure to material in front of hardware (laptops/smart devices). This sometimes invites students to be provoked several times to open other sites besides the learning site to reduce boredom while attending online lectures. This can be supported because these students use more than one device in online learning, for example, laptops and smart devices. So, when they feel bored with presenting material through a zoom meeting on their laptop device, they divert the boredom by opening another site on their device. However, other students stated that they were not at all diverted from opening other sites because they only used one device to participate in online learning, namely a smartphone. If they open another site, it will certainly interfere with their online learning, especially if they are afraid of losing their connection because of their hardware (smartphone) specifications. Does not support opening more than one web page, and if you can, it will make the device work more heavily and very slowly.

Figure 3. Questionnaire tabulation data for attention is easily distracted

3.1.2. Psychological problems of students

The challenges of online learning in the context of students' psychological problems are more specifically described in 2 component items made in the form of statements on the questionnaire. The results of each component will be discussed in more detail in the sections below:

a. Limitations of direct interaction in online learning

To obtain data on the problem component of the limitation of direct interaction in online learning, a questionnaire made up of 4 statements was used. The first point of the statement is to explore data about limited interactions in learning English online. The desired interaction in this statement refers to engaging in discussions and talks with groups of people, as well as posing questions and engaging in chats with coworkers. The acquired data indicate that 1% of students strongly disagree, 9% disagree, and 26% are indecisive. 47% choose for agreement while 17% go for strong agreement.

The second questionnaire item for this component aims to explore data related to the limited opportunities obtained to interact directly and freely with lecturers and between students. The questionnaire findings indicate that 5% of students selected the option "strongly disagree". Their ability to engage in direct and unrestricted interactions with professors and fellow students is restricted. 13% choose to disagree, 16% choose not sure, 36% choose to agree and 30% choose strongly agree.

To enrich the data obtained in this component, the third statement item in the questionnaire was also given to students. This statement item will explore more deeply interactions in the form of feedback or clarifications that are less than optimal from lecturers or colleagues in online English learning. It is evident that 3% of students responded with a significant disagreement. 15% of the pupils responded with a disagreeing answer. 11% of students responded with uncertainty 18% of students responded affirmatively, whereas 53% responded strongly affirmatively.

b. Online learning reduces students' interest in learning

The questionnaire consists of statements that aim to gather information regarding students' diminished motivation and engagement in online English study, which in turn affects their overall interest in the subject. The graphic illustrates that 9% of students responded with a strong disagreement, 22% with a disagreement, 36% with doubt, 19% with agreement, and 14% with a strong agreement. In relation to the questionnaire data above, the same data is also confirmed from the results of the questionnaire. In terms of learning motivation with online learning, students stated that actually, the online English learning system can

provide them with learning motivation. But on the other hand, there are other things that make them less motivated. This can be seen in the interview excerpt below.

P3: ... for myself, the influence of learning English personality development courses online for myself may also have two things. So first, I also like to increase their interest in learning English, for example, when I miss giving a quiz, it seems like there is a challenge, right, especially now that I'm at home, so it's like there is a challenge when there is a quiz at Schoology, reading the material is finished So, to immediately get the value out, immediately see the results that you are doing right away, it can be a challenge in itself, so it's just fun. So it's exciting for him, but sometimes there's something wrong, there are times when he's not enthusiastic, so he's not passionate enough to learn English, because online you can't meet up with friends while studying, miss, the vibe is just different. And this may have something to do with other obstacles, such as technical problems such as internet connection problems, and virtual meetings being ineffective, maybe it's also because of the influence of other courses in the Study Program which also have a lot of workloads. What's more, if you take it now, there are 24 credits, maybe you can't manage time, miss, from me, so far it's still fine, thank you.

From the interview excerpt above, it is clear that learning English online can increase or decrease interest in learning English for college students. The existence of learning activities that are facilitated with automatic assessment features on the application or platform used can increase learning motivation, but on the other hand, learning English online reduces learning motivation because of the lack of opportunities to interact directly in learning with peers and when they are dealing with things. technical barriers that hinder the learning process.

3.1.3. Limitations facilities and infrastructure

The challenges of online learning, notably related to constraints in facilities and infrastructure, are described in two component items presented as statements in the questionnaire. Further elaboration on the outcomes of each element will be provided in the subsequent sections.

a. Devices with limited features (document/video viewer feature, small device memory)

To obtain data on the components of device problems with limited features (document/video opening features, small device memory), a questionnaire made up of 2 statements was used. The first point of the statement is to explore data about the difficulties experienced by students in accessing textbooks in the form of e-books to support online learning. The questionnaire results can be seen in the questionnaire tabulation data in Figure 4.

The Figure 4 questionnaire tabulation data shows the results of the statement items on the questionnaire. From the results obtained, there are 45 (11%) students who choose strongly disagree, 101 (25%) choose to disagree, 118 (29%) choose undecided, 105 (25%) choose to agree and 43 (10%) voted strongly agree. Furthermore, other from the data acquired from the questionnaire responses, there are also data gained from the interviews performed with students. The following is an excerpt from an interview about related data; P11: Besides that, I'm also a bit confused about how to download the book that you gave me because it keeps loading, is it because my connection is bad or because I did it the wrong way, I also don't understand. Thank you

The quote shows that there are obstacles faced by students when utilizing electronic books (e-books) to facilitate online learning by obtaining access to educational texts. As we all know, during this pandemic, lectures take place online. The textbooks utilized are in the format of electronic books, which can be obtained by downloading them from uniform resource locator (URLs) provided by the instructors.

Figure 4. Result questionnaire tabulation data for device

b. Limited budget to get internet quota, and credit

To obtain data on the components of the problem of budget constraints to obtain internet quota, and credit, a questionnaire containing 1 statement was used, namely digging up data about budget limitations in acquiring quotas to access instructional materials during online English instruction. The results of the questionnaire can be seen in Figure 5 questionnaire tabulation data. The Figure 5 questionnaire tabulation data shows the results of the statement items on the questionnaire.

From the Figure 5 obtained, there are 24 (6%) students who choose strongly disagree, 42 (10%) choose to disagree, 63 (15%) choose not sure, 114 (28%) choose to agree and 169 (41%) voted strongly agree. Furthermore, other from the data acquired from the questionnaire responses, there is also data gained from the interviews performed with students. The following is an excerpt from an interview about related data; P2: ...limited quota, the limited internet quota provided by the government is somewhat limited, so I have to buy another internet quota because I have to make assignments like that, miss, the assignments are in video form, and references are in the form of videos so it takes up a lot of quotas, a bit heavy also in terms of expenses, miss, for example, all courses are now online, so the internet provided is limited, miss. P13: But I'll be honest, miss, even though I have no problem with my signal, but... ee... I'm sorry miss, I feel very wasteful with the quota, miss. Right now, all course is online, miss, assignments, videos, materials, and others are all online, so I have to spend a lot of quotas, and that's quite burdensome for my parents, miss. Thank you miss. The results of the interviews show that students experience budget constraints in acquiring allotments to obtain material resources while engaging in online English learning.

Figure 5. Questionnaire tabulation data Limited budget to get internet quota, and credit

3.1.4. Limited internet access

The challenges of online learning in the context of the problem of limited internet access are more specifically described in a component item, namely internet connections that do not reach all areas where students live. The item components are made in 2 forms of statements on the questionnaire. The first point of the statement is about the difficulties in terms of internet networks while participating online learning can be disrupted by an abrupt loss of internet connectivity and secondly the obstacles faced and solution. The data from the questionnaire on this statement item can be seen in Figure 6 questionnaire tabulation data:

Figure 6. Questionnaire tabulation data limited internet access

The Figure 6 questionnaire tabulation data shows the results of the statement items on the questionnaire. From the results obtained, there are 20 (5%) students who choose strongly disagree, 33 (8%) choose to disagree, 95 (23%) choose not sure, 142 (34%) choose to agree and 122 (30%) voted strongly agree. In addition to the data obtained from the results of the questionnaire, there are also data obtained from the results of interviews conducted with students. The following is an excerpt from an interview about related data; P11: Ok miss, I'm trying to respond to your question. What happens during online learning is that the signal is constrained...eee...that is, you often go in and out of your own room. Even until you get out and can't get back in, miss. P14: good afternoon. Here, I am allowed to answer questions from my mother, namely about the difficulties experienced during online lessons, especially in English courses. So, the first thing I experienced was signal problems. In my home area, for example, if I do online lectures using Zoom or Google Meet, sometimes the signal or connection is bad. So, from this problem, lectures became less smooth like that, because there were problems with the signal, so the voice of the mother, when she explained, became disjointed and during discussions, the voices of her friends were also broken. And sometimes it also dies by itself, miss, suddenly it's cut off, miss.

The interview excerpt above shows that the internet network is still a big obstacle in online learning. This is caused by the internet network that is not evenly distributed to remote areas. It caused students to experience difficulties or interference with the internet network, such as the internet network being disconnected suddenly.

3.2. Analysis

The tabulated questionnaire data indicates that the online learning approach is increasingly being embraced and is becoming a regular practice in the existing education system. According to the findings of unstructured interviews, a number of students reported that they had been utilizing the internet approach since the onset of the pandemic, which occurred in early March 2020. The students were mandated to proficiently navigate online learning modalities throughout all courses, utilizing diverse learning platforms as stipulated by the instructor's syllabus. Online learning adheres to the lecturer's provided timetable and can be conducted in any location, such as one's residence or regions with optimal internet connectivity, such as the vicinity of the campus (for individuals residing in Singaraja) or public spaces equipped with wifi access.

The difficulty in adapting to learning becomes the explanation of the statement in the second statement item in the questionnaire. From the tabulated data, it was found that 31% of students agreed with the statement. This proves that the challenge that is often experienced by students is the difficulty of adapting to online learning [44], [45]. The interview findings also indicated that students encountered challenges in adapting to online learning, particularly in their interactions with instructors and participation in discussions.

The obstacles associated with the aforementioned components serve as opportunities for educators to devise engaging adaptations of online learning in order to surmount the aforementioned challenges. In his third point, [46], [47] highlights the challenge of online learning, specifically the need for a more concerted effort in motivating and engaging students through an effective pedagogical method. To enhance student motivation, instructors must consistently generate novel, captivating, and enjoyable online learning experiences in order to mitigate the difficulties outlined in claims two and three. To cultivate motivation in studying, educators must serve as mentors capable of guiding pupils towards the educational setting [48]. The findings of study on the psychological issues faced by students in online learning indicate that students do experience certain psychological phenomena. Overall, according to data gathered from both surveys and interviews, students commonly experience feelings of isolation and lack of motivation.

Online learning creates boundaries that prevent learning interactions from being actualized. One basic thing that contributes to this is the existence of technical problems such as an unstable internet network. This has a negative impact on learning interactions. Students are not free to interact in various forms of activity. From the results of interviews, students felt they could not carry out discussions freely, less intensive group assignments were carried out where based on the results of interviews students preferred to do group assignments outside the network. So, this also indirectly limits their opportunities for collaborative interactions.

Furthermore, the study also highlights the significance of learning motivation, in addition to the absence of interaction. Regarding learning motivation, an intriguing discovery was made through data analysis. Based on the findings of questionnaires and interviews, it is evident that students experience two conflicting emotions. On one hand, learning English online has the potential to inspire and encourage students to engage in the learning process. The results can be inferred from the collection of student responses to the questionnaire items pertaining to English language acquisition through reduced inquiry about learning. The questionnaire results indicated that 9% of students responded with a strong disagreement, 22% responded with a disagreement, 36% responded with uncertainty, 19% responded with agreement, and 14% responded with a strong agreement. This is evidenced by the outcomes of interviews in which students

express that there are certain characteristics of learning activities available on online learning platforms that can enhance student engagement in the learning process. For instance, implementing quizzes or assessments with an automated and transparent scoring system allows students to directly observe the progress of their learning objectives, eliminating the need to rely on the lecturer for evaluation results. This is the factor that drives their personal motivation to engage in the learning process. This finding aligns with the studies conducted by [49], [50], which demonstrate that online learning has the potential to enhance student motivation in the learning process.

The internet infrastructure plays a crucial role in facilitating the process of online education. The uneven distribution of internet connectivity has hindered the seamless progress of online learning. Restricted internet connectivity is a hindrance to the process of acquiring knowledge and skills through online education. The specific constraint being referred to is the lack of internet connectivity in some geographical locations where students reside. Another hindrance in online learning is the sudden disconnection of the internet network, which hampers seamless interactions during the learning process.

4. CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the data analysis and discussion presented in the preceding chapter, it can be inferred that non-English majoring students had numerous problems in online English learning during the COVID-19 pandemic. These challenges narrow down to general dimensions. It can be described as follows; Lack of familiarity with online learning, psychological problems of students, Limited facilities and infrastructure, and limited internet access.

REFERENCES

- [1] B. M. Batubara, "The problems of the world of education in the middle of the covid-19 pandemic," *Budapest International Research and Critics Institute (BIRCI-Journal): Humanities and Social Sciences*, vol. 4, no. 1, pp. 450–457, Jan. 2021, doi: 10.33258/birci.v4i1.1626.
- [2] M. B. N. Wajdi, Iwan Kuswandi, Umar Al Faruq, Z. Zuhijra, K. Khairudin, and K. Khoiriyah, "Education policy overcome coronavirus, a study of Indonesians," *EDUTECH: Journal of Education And Technology*, vol. 3, no. 2, pp. 96–106, Mar. 2020, doi: 10.29062/edu.v3i2.42.
- [3] W. Ali, "Online and remote learning in higher education institutes: a necessity in light of covid-19 pandemic," *Higher Education Studies*, vol. 10, no. 3, p. 16, May 2020, doi: 10.5539/hes.v10n3p16.
- [4] H. Yulia, "Online learning to prevent the spread of pandemic corona virus in indonesia," *ETERNAL (English Teaching Journal)*, vol. 11, no. 1, May 2020, doi: 10.26877/eternal.v11i1.6068.
- [5] H. Shen, M. Fu, H. Pan, Z. Yu, and Y. Chen, "The impact of the covid-19 pandemic on firm performance," *Emerging Markets Finance and Trade*, vol. 56, no. 10, pp. 2213–2230, Aug. 2020, doi: 10.1080/1540496X.2020.1785863.
- [6] Y. Yang and L. F. Cornelious, "Preparing instructors for quality online instruction," *Online Journal of Distance Learning Administration*, vol. 8, no. 1, 2005.
- [7] Permendikbud, *Circular letter of the minister of education and culture no. 4 of 2020 concerning the implementation of education policies during the emergency period of the spread of corona virus disease (covid-19) (in indonesian)*. Pusat Pendidikan Dan Pelatihan Pegawai Kemendikbudristek, 2020. [Online]. Accessed: Feb. 20, 2024, Available: <https://pusdiklat.kemdikbud.go.id/surat-edaran-mendikbud-no-4-tahun-2020-tentang-pelaksanaan-kebijakan-pendidikan-dalam-masa-darurat-penyebaran-corona-virus-disease-covid-1-9/>
- [8] Kemendikbud, *Indonesian students competency assessment report (in Indonesian)*. 2020.
- [9] S. Tadesse and W. Muluye, "The impact of covid-19 pandemic on education system in developing countries: a review," *Open Journal of Social Sciences*, vol. 8, no. 10, pp. 159–170, Sep. 2020, doi: 10.4236/jss.2020.810011.
- [10] S. Anugrah, R. Andika, and N. Hendri, "Circular letter of the minister of education and culture no. 4 of 2020 concerning the implementation of education policies during the emergency period of the spread of corona virus disease (COVID-19)," Atlantis Press, Dec. 2019, pp. 103–106. Accessed: Feb. 17, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.atlantis-press.com/proceedings/icoet-19/125925063>
- [11] T. Panskyi, E. Korzeniewska, M. Serwach, and K. Grudzień, "New realities for polish primary school informatics education affected by covid-19," *Education and Information Technologies*, vol. 27, no. 4, pp. 5005–5032, May 2022, doi: 10.1007/s10639-021-10778-8.
- [12] C. Li and F. Lalani, "The covid-19 pandemic has changed education forever. this is how," *World Economic Forum*. Apr. 2020. Accessed: Feb. 17, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2020/04/coronavirus-education-global-covid19-online-digital-learning/>
- [13] B. Means, Y. Toyama, R. Murphy, M. Bakia, and K. Jones, "Evaluation of evidence-based practices in online learning: a meta-analysis and review of online learning studies," Washington, 2009. [Online]. Accessed: Feb. 22, 2024, Available: <http://eprints.cpkn.ca/7/1/finalreport.pdf>
- [14] B. Gilbert, "Online learning revealing the benefits and challenges," St. John Fisher University, New York, NY, US, 2015. [Online]. Available: https://fisherpub.sjf.edu/education_ETD_masters/303
- [15] M. Suryaman *et al.*, "COVID-19 pandemic and home online learning system: does it affect the quality of pharmacy school learning?," *Systematic Reviews in Pharmacy*, pp. 524–530, 2020, Accessed: Feb. 17, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.31838/srp.2020.8.74>
- [16] A. Akuratiya and N. Meddage, "Students' perception of online learning during covid-19 pandemic: a survey study of it students," *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science (IJRISS)*, vol. IV, no. IX, pp. 755–758, Sep. 2020.
- [17] C. L. Dittoe, "Junior high teachers' perceptions of integrating classroom technology related to the learning management system schoology," ProQuest LLC, 2018.
- [18] L. A. Perguna, N. Apriyanti, and D. Kurniasih, "Alternative online learning using social media as a panacea," *International*

- Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning (iJET)*, vol. 16, no. 07, p. 257, Apr. 2021, doi: 10.3991/ijet.v16i07.21209.
- [19] V. Zulfa and P. Laras, "Schooling and slido: the perfect platform combination for distance learning during the covid-19 pandemic," in *Proceedings of the {International} {Joint} {Conference} on {Science} and {Engineering} ({IJCSSE} 2020)*, Surabaya, East Java, Indonesia: Atlantis Press, 2020, doi: 10.2991/aer.k.201124.016.
- [20] S. Chauhan, "Comprehensive review of coronavirus disease 2019 (covid-19)," *Biomedical Journal*, vol. 43, no. 4, pp. 334–340, Aug. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.bj.2020.05.023.
- [21] K. El Fakiri, H. Nassih, I. Ait Sab, G. Draiss, and M. Bouskraoui, "Epidemiology and clinical features of coronavirus disease 2019 in moroccan children," *Indian Pediatrics*, vol. 57, no. 9, pp. 808–810, Sep. 2020, doi: 10.1007/s13312-020-1958-8.
- [22] N. Morze and E. S. Trybulska, "Web-based community-supported online education during the covid-19 pandemic," *International Journal of Web Based Communities*, vol. 17, no. 1, p. 9, 2021, doi: 10.1504/IJWBC.2021.112858.
- [23] H. Ouassou *et al.*, "The pathogenesis of coronavirus disease 2019 (covid-19): evaluation and prevention," *Journal of Immunology Research*, vol. 2020, p. 1357983, 2020, doi: 10.1155/2020/1357983.
- [24] T. N. C. P. E. R. E. Team, "The epidemiological characteristics of an outbreak of 2019 novel coronavirus diseases (covid-19) — china, 2020," *China CDC Weekly*, vol. 2, no. 8, pp. 113–122, Feb. 2020, Accessed: Feb. 17, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC8392929/>
- [25] "COVID - Coronavirus Statistics - Worldometer." [Online]. accessed Feb. 29, 2024, Available: <https://www.worldometers.info/coronavirus/>
- [26] Y. Guo, "Exploring idiomatic creativity in english as a global language - pitzl marie-luise, creativity in english as a lingua franca: idiom and metaphor. boston: mouton de gruyter, 2018. pp. xiii + 288. hardback £91.00, isbn 978-1-5015-1688-7," *English Today*, vol. 36, no. 1, pp. 58–60, Mar. 2020, doi: 10.1017/S0266078419000178.
- [27] F. MacArthur, "Marie-luise pitzl (2018). creativity in english as a lingua franca: idiom and metaphor," *Metaphor and the Social World*, vol. 9, no. 2, pp. 285–292, Nov. 2019, doi: 10.1075/msw.19008.mac.
- [28] M.-L. Pitzl, *Creativity in english as a lingua franca: idiom and metaphor*. Walter de Gruyter GmbH & Co KG, 2018.
- [29] S. Wright and L. Zheng, "Language as system and language as dialogic creativity," in *The {Routledge} {Handbook} of {English} as a {Lingua} {Franca}*, 1st ed., J. Jenkins, W. Baker, and M. Dewey, Eds., Routledge, 2017, pp. 506–517, doi: 10.4324/9781315717173-41.
- [30] P. Rao, "The role of english as a global language," *Research Journal Of English (RJOE)*, vol. 4, no. 1, pp. 65–79, Jan. 2019.
- [31] M. C. Murray Denise E., *What english language teachers need to know volume iii: designing curriculum*, 2nd ed. New York: Routledge, 2021, doi: 10.4324/9780429275746.
- [32] T. Burner and C. Carlsen, "Teachers' multilingual beliefs and practices in English classrooms: A scoping review," *Rev. Educ.*, vol. 11, no. 2, Aug. 2023, doi: 10.1002/rev3.3407.
- [33] Q. Wen, "The production-oriented approach to teaching university students english in china," *Language Teaching*, vol. 51, no. 4, pp. 526–540, Oct. 2018, doi: 10.1017/S026144481600001X.
- [34] A. Mauranen, "Second language acquisition, world englishes, and english as a lingua franca (elf)," *World Englishes*, vol. 37, no. 1, pp. 106–119, Mar. 2018, doi: 10.1111/weng.12306.
- [35] A. Damayanti, "Reasons why english is important for engineering students," Institute of Technology Sepuluh Nopember, Indonesia, 2021.
- [36] R. M. Simamora, "The challenges of online learning during the covid-19 pandemic: an essay analysis of performing arts education students," *Studies in Learning and Teaching*, vol. 1, no. 2, pp. 86–103, Aug. 2020, doi: 10.46627/silet.v1i2.38.
- [37] S. Kumar Basak, M. Wotto, and P. Bélanger, "E-learning, m-learning and d-learning: conceptual definition and comparative analysis," *E-Learning and Digital Media*, vol. 15, no. 4, pp. 191–216, Jul. 2018, doi: 10.1177/2042753018785180.
- [38] M.-H. Lin, H.-C. Chen, and K.-S. Liu, "A study of the effects of digital learning on learning motivation and learning outcome," *Eurasia Journal of Mathematics, Science and Technology Education*, vol. 13, no. 7, pp. 3553–3564, Jun. 2017, doi: 10.12973/eurasia.2017.00744a.
- [39] M. Igere, "E-learning amongst library science students, case of delta state university, nigeria during covid-19 pandemic lock down: pros and cons," *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)*, Feb. 2021, [Online]. Available: <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/4889>
- [40] V. I. Zygouris-Coe, "Benefits and challenges of collaborative learning in online teacher education," in *Handbook of {Research} on {Emerging} {Practices} and {Methods} for {K}-12 {Online} and {Blended} {Learning}*, IGI Global, 2019, pp. 33–56, doi: 10.4018/978-1-5225-8009-6.ch002.
- [41] H. Sunhaji, M. Misbah, and Nawawi, *Evaluation of the ptkin postgraduate curriculum in the era of the industrial revolution 4.0 (theory and implementation) (in indonesian)*. Banyumas, Indonesia: Zahira Media Publisher, 2021. Accessed: Feb. 17, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://zahiramediapublisher.com/toko-buku-online/evaluasi-kurikulum-pascasarjana-ptkin-di-era-revolusi-industri-40-teori-dan-impleentasinya>
- [42] S. C. Huang, "Language learning strategies in context," *The Language Learning Journal*, vol. 46, no. 5, pp. 647–659, Oct. 2018, doi: 10.1080/09571736.2016.1186723.
- [43] J. Gillett-Swan, "The challenges of online learning: supporting and engaging the isolated learner," *Journal of Learning Design*, vol. 10, no. 1, p. 20, Jan. 2017, doi: 10.5204/jld.v9i3.293.
- [44] J. M. Lodge, G. Kennedy, L. Lockyer, A. Arguel, and M. Pachman, "Understanding difficulties and resulting confusion in learning: an integrative review," *Frontiers in Education*, vol. 3, 2018, Accessed: Feb. 17, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/educ.2018.00049>
- [45] K. Sarah, S. Oceane, F. Emily, and F. Carole, "Learning from lockdown - assessing the positive and negative experiences, and coping strategies of researchers during the covid-19 pandemic," *Applied Animal Behaviour Science*, vol. 236, p. 105269, Mar. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.applanim.2021.105269.
- [46] P. Dillenbourg, D. Schneider, and P. Synteta, "Virtual learning environments," Kastaniotis Editions, Greece, 2002, p. 3. Accessed: Feb. 17, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://telearn.hal.science/hal-00190701>
- [47] Y. Su, C. Zheng, J.-C. Liang, and C.-C. Tsai, "Examining the relationship between english language learners' online self-regulation and their self-efficacy," *Australasian Journal of Educational Technology*, vol. 34, no. 3, Jul. 2018, doi: 10.14742/ajet.3548.
- [48] B. Senjahari, D. Desfitranita, and M. Kustati, "Learning objectives and environments: how do they affect students' motivation in english language learning?," *Studies in English Language and Education*, vol. 8, no. 2, pp. 492–507, May 2021, doi: 10.24815/siele.v8i2.18523.
- [49] H. Abuhassna, W. M. Al-Rahmi, N. Yahya, M. A. Z. M. Zakaria, A. B. M. Kosnin, and M. Darwish, "Development of a new model on utilizing online learning platforms to improve students' academic achievements and satisfaction," *International Journal*

- of Educational Technology in Higher Education*, vol. 17, no. 1, p. 38, Dec. 2020, doi: 10.1186/s41239-020-00216-z.
- [50] H. Baber, "Determinants of students' perceived learning outcome and satisfaction in online learning during the pandemic of covid19," *Journal of Education and e-Learning Research*, vol. 7, no. 3, pp. 285–292, Aug. 2020, doi: 10.20448/journal.509.2020.73.285.292.

BIOGRAPHIES OF AUTHORS

Ketut Susiani is a lecturer at Universitas Pendidikan Ganesha in Singaraja, Bali, Indonesia. She teaches in the Elementary School Teacher Education program. She has a Bachelor's degree and a Master's degree (M.Pd.) in Elementary School Teacher Education. Her research interests include diagnostic science literacy in elementary school students. She can be contacted at email: ketut.susiani@undiksha.ac.id.

Nyoman Dantes is a professor in the Department of Guidance and Counseling. Scientific papers produced from various types of science as well as books published on research methodology, evaluation, and several other topics. His scientific writings are published in reputable national and international journals. He can be contacted at email: dantes@undiksha.ac.id.

Ida Bagus Putu Arnyana is a professor at the Faculty of Science. His scientific papers are published in reputable national and international journals. Apart from actively writing articles, he also teaches according to his scientific field and writes books that are relevant to his scientific field and books that are outside his scientific field. He can be contacted at email: putu.arnyana@undiksha.ac.id.

Ni Ketut Suarni is a professor in the Department of Guidance and Counseling. Scientific papers are produced from various types of science as well as published books on psychology, student development, and several other topics. Her scientific writings are published in reputable national and international journals. She can be contacted at email: niketut.suarni@undiksha.ac.id.

Kadek Suranata is a lecturer with the positions of professor, researcher, and practitioner in the field of counseling and psychotherapy. Currently he serves as a lecturer at the Universitas Pendidikan Ganesha, Bali, Indonesia. He teaches Guidance Counseling (Guidance Counseling) in the undergraduate program. Suranata has a Bachelor's and Master's degree in Counseling Guidance. He also holds a doctoral degree in guidance and counseling. His research interests include exploring elementary school students' learning difficulties and risks in mathematics based on mathematics anxiety, self-efficacy, and smart resilience, and many works have been published in accredited Scopus international and national journals. He can be contacted at email: kadek.suranata@undiksha.ac.id.

I Kadek Suartama is a lecturer in the Department of Education Technology at the Universitas Pendidikan Ganesha. He researched various fields of science such as; IT, media, and other fields. he studied doctoral program at the University of Malang. He has various scientific papers published in reputable national journals and Scopus indexed international. He can be contacted at email: ik-suartama@undiksha.ac.id.

Alexander Hamonangan Simamora currently a lecturer in the Department of Educational Technology, Faculty of Educational Sciences, Universitas Pendidikan Ganesha. The main research direction is digital learning and e-learning. He can be contacted at email: alexander.simamora@undiksha.ac.id.